

The Importance of teaching vocabulary to young learners during English lessons.

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Annotation: This article will discuss the importance of teaching English vocabulary to young learners and also about some techniques of teaching vocabulary to young learners.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы обсудим важность преподавания английской лексики юным ученикам, а также о некоторых методах обучения лексике.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yosh o'quvchilarga ingliz tili lug'atini o'rgatishning ahamiyati, shuningdek, yosh o'quvchilarga lug'atni o'rgatishning ba'zi usullari haqida so'z boradi.

Key words: Young learners, techniques, vocabulary

Ключевые слова: Юные ученики, техники, лексика.

Kalit so'zlar: Yosh o'quvchilar, texnikalar, lug'at.

Introduction

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It is very important for all people who learn a language to understand and improve vocabularies

because the more vocabulary we know the better we can understand the meaning of the words. To improve and enrich our vocabularies there are some ways, for example by vocabulary.

Name animal, media picture to get many words. Teachers have the important role to build children's vocabularies. They should know the factors in teaching such as

methods, strategies, techniques, and materials, so that the teacher can convey the materials well in accordance with children's characteristics.

According to Evan and Lang (2006) said that a good method was useless in teacher's

hand who did not know how to use it and a good teacher could not be effective if she/he used a bad method. Some experts have formulated some possible techniques that can be considered good and can be implemented to the TEYL, class especially in teaching vocabulary. The

research is intended to discover of the teaching English vocabulary to young learners in a

Elementary Padasuka 2, and to investigate the "The Teaching of English Vocabulary to Young

Learners. Based on the description above, this study highlights teacher's difficulties in teaching English vocabulary to young learners in the classroom.

And to cope with the difficulties English teacher can possibly design suitable teaching techniques to be implemented in their classes. Some experts have formulated some possible techniques that can be considered good and can be implemented to the TEYL, class especially in teaching vocabulary. The research is intended to discover of the teaching English vocabulary to young learners in a Elementary

Padasuka 2, and to investigate the techniques used by some the teaching of English vocabulary to young learners.

Vocabulary

Vocabulary is the stock of words which are at disposal of speaker of writer. The term

of vocabulary may refer to all words in the whole language, at the words or phrase used in particular varieties such as dialect, register and terminology. Along the

lines of Hartman's statement, Spencer (1992) mentioned vocabulary as the highest ability to master for a reader or a writer, words which are used in the subject of knowledge, and a list of words which is arranged such as in dictionary, complete with a clear and short explanation.

In teaching vocabulary, teachers should know what of vocabulary to be taught.

According to Finocchiaro (1989: 21, cited from Fadillah, 2011) vocabulary is divided into two types: Function word. It needs to be learned as quickly as feasible (in a logical order and sequence, however) and Content word. It can be learned in small groups around "life" situations.

2. Techniques of Teaching Vocabulary

As mentioned above, there are three main stages in teaching vocabulary. In other word, there is some common techniques used in each stage as follow: Techniques in Presenting. Yet it is the important stage that the student is introduced with the new words. As an English teacher, we should know the techniques of teaching vocabulary which are suitable for the students. Techniques in Practicing. In practicing stage, there are a variety of tasks which can be used in order to help move words into long-term memory.

Media is a main instrument in teaching and learning process. It is used to attract the students' attention and deliver the information easily. Teachers of young learners have to use

some visuals in their teaching activities to facilitate their teaching. According to Wright, there are various kinds of media, but visual is appropriate media for young learners in learning vocabulary.

3 Young learners. Characteristic of young learners are different from old learners. They are five to fourteen years of age (Pinter, 2006: 1). In this age they find difficulty to know abstract thing

because

they have a limited knowledge about the word. In teaching vocabulary to young learners. As teacher we all know what we should do in our preparation before teaching in the classroom such as make lesson plan, prepare some aid for teaching and many else. Every teacher will do their own way to teaching English but basically they do the same thing like others as their method in teaching English.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that it is crucial to learn vocabulary for young learners during their English learning journey.

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